

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PREPOSITIONAL CONSTRUCTION “ON” IN SHAPING
THE MEANING OF THE SENTENCE

Jumanazarov Samandar Urinovich

Teacher of foreign languages Karshi engineering-economics institute

jumanazarovsamandar45@gmail.com

Abstract: *The emphasis is on determining the space, time, and conceptual features of the prepositions. We will try to find a database of the linguistic consciousness by studying the functional use of specific lexical units. The article presents theoretical ideas in this regard and proves them with examples.*

Keywords: *application; contraction; extralinguistic; outrageous; geometric; grammaticized; syntax; morphological; incompatible*

Grammatical construction can be evaluated as a property of prepositions. In general, the grammatical process is understood as a historical process by identifying grammatical unity that is not a grammatical language, which is a process of identifying grammatical features existing in this unit. Thus, grammar can be regarded as an inexhaustible process to enhance the grammatical features of language units. Nouns that refer to human body meanings can be examples of grammar. Moreover, English language prepositions, adverbial elements also take an active part in this process. Additionally, it is possible to observe aspects of the grammatical process in prepositions related to space relations. As you can see, the English language prepositions have expanded its functional application in the process of historical development. As a result, it is possible to notice that prepositions, which do not have any meaning in space, are then reflected in these characteristics. It is possible to say that this phenomenon is the same as the prepositions. All prepositions in English are meaningful. In addition to their lexical-semantic features, they are grammatical and also imaginative schematic. The meaning of the prepositions and their relationship to the subject can be directly monitored by many studies and linguists, including B.Pote, R. Wagner, B.Brendel and other linguists. Separate grouping of semantic characters of each predictor in their work is aimed at identifying meaning in the context of speech. The emphasis is on determining the space, time, and conceptual features of the prepositions. We will try to find a database of the linguistic consciousness by studying the functional use of specific lexical units. The semantic analysis of the presence of fragmentary words at different times, along with the opportunity to observe the evolutionary development of these words, also provides an opportunity to cover the aspects of their extralinguistic connotations. It also gives a chance to learn the concepts that are based on specific words. The key features of the predecessors are also important in emphasizing the functional significance of the lexical concepts. They include the functional information of lexical concepts as the main parameters of space geometric parameters. In particular, prepositions can be used for the meaning that refer to the concept of space. This predicate represents the location of the subject at the top of another preposition. If the geometric parameter is a contact, the functional parameter is a point of reference and linguistic content. For example, *the apple is on the table*. Of course, the content of the lexical unit and the content of the parameters may be disclosed. For example, if the apple on the wall seems to be right from the linguistic point of view, the meaning is unreasonable, for the apple to remain on the wall should

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-6

be either glued or hanging. in this case, the content and linguistic notion are incompatible. However, the existence of the concept of basic is important in establishing the consistence of the content and linguistic concept. Look at the examples *on one's feet / knees / legs / back, on tiptoe, on all fours*. In these examples, human body parts serve as the basis, So it is possible to observe the relationship between the contact parameters and the base parameter and the linguistic content of these compounds. It also refers to the meaning of the means of movement. In this context the contact parameters and base parameters are not important on foot / horseback, on the bus and so on. but in this context the lexical basis is assumed to be predominant. The following is an example of the underlying characteristic that is expressed in the following example: the earth turns on its axis. In this example, the support point is reflected in its axis combination. Another meaning of preposition "on" is of dependency which can be proved with the following examples: Are you on heroine? or she is on the pill. In the meaning of the person's dependence on something expressed in the noun. In this case, the preposition is a semi-lexical property. The psychological basis of the psychological dependency of the person. for example you can count / rely on my vote. Rationale or epistemic base values are reflected on / on purpose combinations. If we focus on the content and content of the examples, then we can see that there are not only basic contact parameters, but also other resources. The prepositions also predict the concept of the state of affairs. For example, "as far as she was capable of love, she loved her, and her hand on her arm, she addressed her in a muted reluctant voice, the nearest she could get to tenderness". Functionally predetermined, is also used to refer to the expression of the duration of the activity associated with the activation. For example: *But I suppose some women do go on like that. Burden whose expression conveyed that he was rather approved by women who went on like that*. These terms are used in the term "functional activity", because such combinations indicate the state of the statistical character of physical activity, such as technical movable statisticality. For example, *The angela's prints were on the backdoor, the dord from the kitchen in the hallway, each bedroom door and a variety of bottles and jars on each dressing table. a marvelous was dawning on her*. According to V.Evies, the prepositions have an activity icon. According to the scientist, the switching point means activating electrical equipment, i.e moving from static to dynamic. In this case depends on the functional and semantic nature of the transformation of the preposition. It acts as a reference point of the transformation of the action point of the verb. The switch statement in the combination is interpreted as a transformative character. In other words, the lexical concepts associated with the predetermination provide the functional movement parameters and correspond to the linguistic meaning. For example: *you would know who would be likely to call it or be fetched home by her. Tell me who came to your house. what friends or acquaintances called your wife? I dont think there is always a time till now, when i have had a reasonable amount of money to live on and now. we were on our beam ends. Angela couldnt walk*. In these cases, the units associated with the preceding are referred to as the word combination or attributes, which have the meaning of action. and the occurrence of the meaning of the state of affairs in the particular case is consistent with the temporal significance. it can be seen that the situation or event occurring within a limited period of time. the following examples will be considered:

- a. on fire
- b. on live (sports game)
- c. on tap (beer is available)

- d. on sleep (as in an alarm clock)
- e. on pause (as in a DVD player)
- f. on sale
- g. on loan
- h. on alert
- i. on best behaviour
- j. look out on the move
- k. on the wane m. on the run.

REFERENCES

1. Bennett, D. C. 1975. *Spatial and Temporal Uses of English Prepositions: An Essay in Stratificational Semantics*. London: Longman.
2. Bowerman, M. 1996. *Learning how to structure for language: a crosslinguistic perspective*.
3. Brugman, C. 1988. *The Story of Over: Polysemy, Semantics, and the Structure of the Lexicon*. New York: Garland.
4. S. U. Jumanazarov. (2022). Acquisition of writing in the early stages of learning English
5. Jackendoff, R. (1983). *Semantics and cognition*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
6. Chomskiy, N. 1965 *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*, Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
7. Fauconnier, G. 1985 *Mental Spaces: Aspects of Meaning Construction in Natural Language*, Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press.
8. Fauconnier, G. & E. Sweetser (eds.) 1996 *Spaces, Worlds, and Grammar*, Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
9. Jumanazarov Samandar Urinovich. (2023). Use of internet resources in the process of learning english as a foreign language.
10. Fauconnier, G. & M. Turner 1994 *Conceptual Projection and Middle Spaces*', Report 9401, Department of Cognitive Science, UCSD.
11. Quirk et al., 1985 *A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*, London: Longman.
12. Sinha, C. & L. A. Thorseng, 1995, 'A Coding System for Spatial Relational Reference', *Cognitive Linguistics*, 6-2/3, 261-309.
13. R.Kiyamov. Karshi – 2009. Лингвистический анализ предложных сочетаний в современном английском языке.
14. Jumanazarov Samandar Urinovich. (2023). General information about prepositions and lexical, syntactic and semantic features of verbs.